

PROJECT MANAGEMENT FOR RESEARCH SOFTWARE

PEOPLE AND PROCESSES

BIRDS OF A FEATHER SESSION, RSECON24

SARAH JAFFA

AGENDA

- Why do we care about project management?
 - What, why and when of Agile
 - Mike Simpson – Task Management for Self Care
 - Ann Gledson – Scrum for RSEs at UoM
 - Monika Byrne Svata and Jonathan Cooper – Agile Management of Research Projects at UCL ARC
 - Questions for presenters
 - Group discussion
-

WHAT, WHY AND WHEN OF AGILE

Waterfall

- “Traditional” project management (~1950s)
- Planning-heavy, regulated, safety-critical
- Large scale engineering projects

vs

Agile

- Iterative, incremental software development (~1950s)
- Agile Manifesto - 2001
 - **Individuals and interactions** over processes and tools
 - **Working software** over comprehensive documentation
 - **Customer collaboration** over contract negotiation
 - **Responding to change** over following a plan
- Many flavours of Agile
 - Scrum, Kanban, XP, Lean, SAFe...
 - Each designed for a different situation (or to sell another book/course?)

WHAT, WHY AND WHEN OF AGILE

When is Agile better than Waterfall?

- No regulations requiring pre-approval of plans
- Incremental feedback is possible
 - Smaller chunks make some physical sense
 - Customer feedback is available
- Moving target
 - Requirements are uncertain OR
 - Market (value) is changeable
- You have an engaged proactive team with the right skills

Manifesto:

Working software over comprehensive documentation

Customer collaboration over contract negotiation

Responding to change over following a plan

Individuals and interactions over processes and tools

“Tools and processes are important, but it is more important to have competent people working together effectively” –

Scott Ambler, Examining the Agile Manifesto

PRESENTATIONS

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- Please ask questions on Canapii and we will answer them after all 3 presentations
- Join the RSECon24 Slack **#bof-project-management-in-research-software** channel for further questions

GROUP DISCUSSION

- **Introductions:**
 - Name, pronouns, role, affiliation. What project management experience do you have?
 - Why are you here today? What are you hoping to share or learn?
- **Solutions**
 - What project management tools or systems have you tried? (As manager or team member!)
 - What were the advantages and disadvantages?
- **Problems**
 - What do you find difficult, frustrating or stressful in running projects?
 - What training, support or resources do you need to tackle this problem? How could the SIG help you?

THANK YOU

- Thanks to Mike, Ann, Jonathan, and Monika for their contributions
- Thanks to the RSECon24 organisers and volunteers
- Thanks to you all for participating and contributing!

- Join the RSECon24 Slack **#bof-project-management-in-research-software** channel for further questions
- Join the RSE Society Slack **#project-management-sig** for resources, discussions and events

